

Evidence for humans sharing DNA with Saiyans:

1. Saiyans and humans look alike and they share anatomy except for the tail (anatomy is linked to genetics)
2. They share basic chromosomes like chromosome 1, 2, and 19 which helps with muscle development in both humans and Saiyans
3. Humans actually have tail bones
4. Both humans and Saiyans are sapient humanoids
5. Both came from monkeys/apes
6. Even though Saiyans may be fictional, they still have a created set of DNA that can match up with humans

A zoologist approved of how Saiyans share DNA with humans

A zoologist explained how humans emerged from the union of monkeys and Saiyans. Monkeys found new land unaware of the existing Saiyans. A territorial war ensued with casualties on both sides. The conflict ended when a monkey and a Saiyan bred together. Their hybrid offspring were called humans, indicating human DNA has Saiyan origins.

Evidence for humans being part Saiyan:

1. Everything comes from stardust
2. Both humans and Saiyans are made up of atoms (even if Saiyans are on the TV, the light making them is still made up of atoms)
3. Being part Saiyan basically means just at least a single part of a Saiyan being a part of you (even just 1 proton)

It is officially scientifically proven (indirectly) that humans are part Saiyan. Thoughts in your head are scientifically proven to be physically a part of you as stated in <https://www.sciencealert.com/a-neuroscientist-explains-how-your-brain-actually-thinks> , so a thought of a Saiyan is physically a part of you making you part Saiyan. When you think about something, your brain produces neurons of that thought. Those neurons are physically made up of atoms and are inside your brain. Those neurons belong to you since they are in your brain. This means that those neurons are physically a part of you. When you think about Saiyans, your brain produces neurons with the Saiyan thoughts in them. Since Saiyans are originally thoughts/imagination in your head, those neurons are basically carrying Saiyans in a way. And since those Saiyan neurons are physically a part of you, you are part Saiyan. In general, humans have pretty much the most powerful brains ever known. This means that humans are extremely smart. And because humans are so smart, their brains even have the power to imagine. This extraordinary ability allows them to create things in their head and visualize them. This whole process of imagination allows them to create neurons with the new thoughts in their head. With this happening, those new thoughts are physically a part of them. This means that with this superpower that humans have, they can simply become part Saiyan by imagining a Saiyan and letting their brains make a neuron with the Saiyan in it.

Two scientific people who used to be a scientist in the past approved of this. One of them even said that the electric signals in your head with the Saiyan thoughts are some sort of qi energy and that this is related to qi.

Evidence for ki/chi/qi energy being real:

1. Acupuncture works, and it is directly related to ki
2. Ki is basically life energy, and energy is already scientifically proven to be real (why would energy be fake when it's called ki and real when it's called energy)